

Transport Media For Avulsed Teeth: A Review

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Abstract

Aim Dental avulsion causes the complete displacement of the tooth from its socket in the alveolar bone. Immediate replantation is the recommended treatment of choice for an avulsed permanent tooth. To achieve a more favorable prognosis following tooth replantation, use of an appropriate interim transport is usually advocated. Numerous studies have researched and advocated the use of media like saliva, milk, HBSS and ViaSpan. The purpose of the present study is to evaluate the various storage medium for avulsed teeth in terms of efficacy, characteristics and accessibility.

Methodology The articles published in English from 1980 to 2019 in PubMed/MEDLINE, and Google Scholar databases were searched electronically, using 'storage medium', 'avulsed teeth', 'replantation', 'extra-alveolar time' and 'PDL cells' as search terms. 29 papers were selected after application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were critically reviewed for comparison of the outcomes.

Results Our review study showed that the efficacy of milk in maintaining the viability of human PDL cells is similar to that of HBSS as reference solution ($P < 0.05$) and higher than that of coconut water, green tea and egg white. The smallest number of viable cells observed in tap water ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion It can be concluded that milk is the most frequently recommended and with the best prognosis among other solutions that are likely to be available at the scene of an accident, such as water, saline or saliva.

Key words: avulsed teeth, storage medium, replantation

Introduction

Tooth avulsion is a complex traumatic injury characterized by the rupture of the neurovascular bundle and periodontal ligament (PDL) exposing the tooth to the outer environment. The ideal treatment for an avulsed permanent tooth is its immediate replantation, which rarely occurs due to factors associated to the accident itself. Thus a medium should be used for temporary storage during the time elapsed between avulsion and replantation. The characteristics of an ideal storage medium included; capable of maintaining PDL and pulp cell viability, presenting clonogenicity capacity, antioxidant property, no or minimal microbial contamination, compatible physiological pH and osmolality, high availability, ready accessibility and low cost. Different types of wet storage media have been designed specifically for avulsed teeth. These storage media can be purchased in the form of retail product, although such products will not be readily available at the moment of the accident. This study reviews the literature on the different storage media with respect to the characteristics, efficacy and ease of access of the storage medium.

Methodology

The study was a review of articles published in the English language from 1980 to 2019. The PubMed/MEDLINE, Google Scholar databases were searched electronically, using 'storage medium', 'avulsed teeth', 'replantation', and 'PDL cells' as search terms. From a total of 126 papers, 29 articles were selected after application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were critically reviewed for comparison of the outcomes.

Conclusion

Taking together the characteristics, efficacy and availability and accessibility, milk appears as the best indication of a temporary storage medium for avulsed teeth before replantation, and its use is recommended by the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry.

Reference

Sigalas E, Regan JD, Kramer PR, Witherspoon DE, Opperman LA. Survival of human periodontal ligament cells in media proposed for transport of avulsed teeth. *Dental Traumatology* 2004;20:21-28

Results

The outcome of assessment of the designated studies displays below (table 1).

Table 1. Main characteristics, efficacy and accessibility of each storage media

Storage Media	Characteristics	Efficacy	Accessibility
<i>HBSS</i>	Physiological PH, osmolality, nutrients	Excellent	--
<i>Viaspan</i>	Physiological PH, osmolality, favorable to cell growth	Excellent	--
<i>Euro-Collins</i>	Physiological PH and hypothermal capacity	Excellent	--
<i>MEM</i>	Nutrients, antimicrobial, growth factors	Excellent	--
<i>Milk</i>	Small bacterial contents, isotonic, physiological PH, osmolality, growth factors, nutrients	Excellent	+
<i>Green Tea</i>	Antioxidant, antiinflammatory, and antibacterial properties	Excellent	-
<i>Propolis</i>	Antiinflammatory, antibacterial, and antioxidant properties	Excellent	-
<i>Coconut Water</i>	Sterile, natural product, contains nutrients	Good	+
<i>Egg White</i>	Low microbial contamination, contains nutrients and water	Good	+
<i>Ricetral</i>	Essential cells and nutrients	Good	+
<i>Saline</i>	Physiological PH and osmolality	Poor	+
<i>Gatorade</i>	Low PH and hypertonic	Poor	+
<i>Contact Lens Liquid</i>	Antimicrobial property, preservatives	Poor	+
<i>Water</i>	Microbial contamination, hypotonic, non physiological PH, and osmolality	Very poor	++
<i>Saliva</i>	Microbial contamination, hypotonic, non physiological PH, and osmolality	Very poor	++

Discussion

The medium used for temporary storage of avulsed teeth is one of the essential factors that may contribute to accelerate or minimize the occurrence of root resorption or ankylosis following replantation of avulsed teeth. Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) has been widely employed as a reference solution in studies on dental avulsion. Hwang et al reported 94% cell viability after storage of cultured human PDL cells for 24 h in this medium, However its use is restricted to laboratory environments and is not available at an accident site, which makes it impracticable as a medium. MEM cell culture medium, Viaspan have peculiar characteristics that allow maintaining cell viability, minimize tooth injuries involving the permanent dentition, but their lack of availability and high cost make their routine use unviable. Water and saliva are similar and cause a rapid lysis of the cell membrane, have pH and osmolality incompatible to the cells, in addition to being contaminated media. The antibacterial and antiinflammatory actions of green tea and propolis demonstrate their capacity to inhibit prostaglandin synthesis, aiding the immune system in the phagocytic activity and promoting healing effects in the epithelial tissue, although their lack of availability limit their indication. Egg white shows a small loss of efficacy overtime as a storage media, possibly due to egg's high pH and also because the PDL cells could target the several egg proteins as strange bodies. Milk found to have several favorable characteristics as a storage medium for avulsed teeth, as it is an isotonic liquid with an approximately neutral pH and physiological osmolality, has low or no bacterial content, contains growth factors and essential nutrients for cells, in addition to having a high availability mostly everywhere and low cost. Being a gland secretion, milk contains epithelial growth factor, which stimulates the proliferation and regeneration of epithelial cell rests of Malassez and activates the alveolar bone resorption. This will ultimately contribute to isolate the bone tissue from the tooth and decrease the likelihood of ankylosis. In spite of offering no conditions for the restoration of cell morphology nor cell differentiation or mitosis, milk prevents cell death.